

RESEARCH ARTICLE

The Unforgettable Women of History in India: Untold Narratives of Courage and Resilience

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the contributions of women in India's struggle for freedom. India has witnessed the rise of numerous valiant women who have shattered gender norms and stepped onto the battlefield to protect their people, culture and kingdoms. These warrior women, whose tales of bravery echo through the annals of time, remain an inspiration for generations to come. The present paper delves into the narratives of some of the iconic figures, in order to explore the lives of some of the unforgettable women, who defied societal expectations to defend their realms namely: Rani Durgavati, Rani Mangammal, Ahilya Bai Holkar, Kittur Rani Chennamma and Rani Lakshmi Bai. These women faced many challenges in their quest to defend their kingdoms and were known for their exceptional administrative acumen and military prowess. Overcoming the prejudices of their own societies and overcoming adversity yielded remarkable outcomes. The purpose of this paper is to examine these extraordinary women, their indomitable spirit and resilience, who have become our beacons of inspiration, motivating the women kind to rise for their own rights and liberties. Their unwavering commitment undoubtedly played a role in shaping the very course of history. Their narratives resonating across the globe continue to ignite the flames of courage and determination in the hearts of people everywhere.

Keywords: determination, extraordinary, bravery, prowess, warriors

FULL RESEARCH PAPER**Introduction**

The position of women in a society is usually regarded as a fair index of the excellence of its culture and the character of its civilisation. The history of India concerns the history of men who were in charge. Largely forgotten are the lives of the women who, even centuries earlier, shaped the fates of their entire kingdom. A matter of observation and undeniable fact is that we know very little about the actual lives of many of these great women who flourished in India. It is interesting to examine the motive forces behind their lives or the gradual growth of their moral virtues and mental powers, which can indeed stimulate or inspire others by example. For hundreds of years, many Indian women have ruled India, serving as a real source of delight and inspiration. Some have ruled independently, as regents or titled rulers. This study includes the historical narratives of five women who have ruled directly. The panorama of great women of India presented in this article can evoke profound interest spanning the period from the 16th century (1524) to the 19th century (1858).

It is necessary to make an objective study of the womanhood of India. The present paper delves into the narratives of iconic figures to explore the lives of unforgettable women who defied societal expectations to defend their realms, namely: Rani Durgavati, Rani Mangammal, Rani Ahilya Bai Holkar, Kittur Rani Chennamma and Rani Lakshmi Bai. This paper examines the lives and achievements of these five visionary women, their hopes and aspirations, dreams and visions, to evoke among the women community a sense of courage, consciousness, a spirit of resilience and emancipation from barriers of any kind.

Review of Literature

India has a rich history with innumerable stories of powerful and inspiring women who have shaped the boundaries of the country's cultural, social and political landscape. Countless challenges and barriers have faced women. Deepti Priya Mehrotra, in *Her Stories: Indian Women Down the Ages: Thinkers, Workers, Rebels, Queens*, sheds light on the amazing women across three millennia, from the 2nd millennium BCE to the mid-19th century. She remarks, "The more I read history, the less it seemed. I knew about women." (3) Each woman profiled in her book reflects a protagonist of her times that can help shape the world or reconstruct their lives and times. Mehrotra remarks that "Many of our foremothers emerge as gutsy, often startling in their originality, independence and derring-do". (3)

Bhavani Sundaram highlights the perseverance and dedication of all the unseen and unheard women warriors of Independent India, recounting the sacrifices they have made for the freedom of our country. A Survey of the position and prospects of women in Indian society over the last five thousand years is offered in an edited book by Swami Madhavananda and Ramesh Chandra Majumdar. It offers a fascinating picture, or indeed a long procession of Indian women who have attained greatness, with the encouragement of their men in some cases, or, in others, by sheer dint of their own courage and perseverance.

Research Methodology

This article adopts a qualitative in-depth analysis of the lives and contributions of some unforgettable women in Indian history. These five women are national heroines, and innumerable books and legends have been written about them. This study incorporates a narrative account of these women from contemporary texts, accounts by foreign travellers and secondary sources.

Findings

The present paper delves into the narratives of some of the iconic figures, in order to explore the lives of some of the unforgettable women who defied societal expectations to defend their realms, namely:

Rani Durgavati: (1524-1564)

According to Akbarnama, which chronicles the reign of Akbar: Durgavati Was distinguished for her courage, counsel and munificence, and by virtue of these select qualities she brought the whole of that country under her sway.... Did great things by dint of her far-seeing abilities... was always victorious....and did not submit herself at the threshold of the Shahan shah. Rani Durgavati (r. 1550-64 CE) was born into the Rajput Chandela dynasty. She ruled her husband's kingdom of Gondwana, a part of the legends of her region, Jabalpur, and the Mughals and the British chronicled her story. She was inspired by a genuine sense of loyalty to her country in the 16th century.

Daughter of Chandella Rajput king, who ruled a small kingdom, Mahoba, she was endowed with loveliness and grace, fine accomplishments, unflinching determination, and selfless heroism. Not only did she repulse an attack on the kingdom of Gondwana by Baz Bahadur of Malwa, but she also defended her place against external rule. In a collection of history written during the Mughal era, Gondwana was "Immune from external control, the kingdom, extending for three

hundred miles in length and one hundred miles in breadth and with about seventy thousand well-inhabited towns and villages, was abounding in wealth (Muntakhab-ut-Tawarikh 65)

The reigning king of this area, Bir Narayan, was a minor, but her mother, Rani Durgavati, was governing it with skill and courage. According to Abdul Fazl, "she neglected no point of courage or capacity, and did great things by dint of her far-seeing abilities." She always emerged victorious in her conquests. Durgavati always opposed the imperial army. A word of caution to one of her officers: "Twas better to die with glory than live with ignominy. If the just king were here in person, it would have been proper for her to wait upon him.... It was altogether best that she should die bravely."

Putting on her armour, she mounted on an elephant with her bow and quiver lying by her side, and with "a burnished lance" in her hand, the Rani herself led the troops. Her army defeated the Mughal invaders twice successively. When fighting resumed the next day, her son Narayan was wounded. Thereafter, most of her followers deserted the fields. However, fearlessly, she mounted an elephant and fought with utmost bravery until two arrow shots disabled her. One of her faithful officers wanted to carry her from the field to a place of safety. However, she was not ready instead retorted "Today is a day in which I am overcome in battle, God forbid that I be also overcome in name and honour, and that I fall into the hands of the enemy; act like a faithful servant, and dispose of me by this sharp dagger". In the true spirit of Rajput descent, Rani Durgavati preferred death to disgrace and stabbed herself. At last "her end was as noble and devoted as her life had been useful". Sleeman who was assigned administrative work in this area observes in his famous book entitled *Rambles and Recollections of an Indian Official*: "Her tomb is still to be seen where she fell, in a narrow defile between the hills; and the memory of this noble lady has been justly cherished by posterity with feelings of admiration" (Madhavananda 325).

Rani Mangammal: (1652-1704)

A contemporary writer, Chinna Venkanna, throws light on Rani Mangamma's life. She was the daughter of Tupakula Lingama Nayaka of Chandragiri, and a courtesan of Tiruvellorey (Chingleput district) called Kanaka. Beautiful and accomplished, young Mangamma survived and, after her husband died in 1689, ruled the kingdom until 1707 as regent during the minority of her grandson, Vijayaranga Chokkanatha Nayaka. The time when she ruled was a critical period for the Nayaka

Kingdom as it was threatened on the one side by the Mughal forces of Aurangzeb and on the other by the rulers of Mysore, Tanjore, Ramnad and Travancore. Mangamma's means of survival was to acknowledge the supremacy of the Mughal emperor by paying him an annual tribute, as well as to secure the goodwill of his officers and generals with suitable presents and bribes.

Adopting the policy of firmness, she successfully waged wars against her other enemies. At certain points in time, she had to buy off some of them with bribes, and when she felt strong enough, she overpowered the enemy and exacted compensation. Mangamma's name is a household word in the South Tamil country. There still exist numerous avenues, choultries (dharmashalas), and Nayaka palaces within the fort area of Trichy, built by her. These monuments signify the greatness of her rule. Her benefactions to temples and gifts to agraharams for learned brahmanas were numerous; equally liberal were her endowments to Christian churches and Muslim dargahs. Conflicting reports about the end of her reign account that power was forcibly wrested from her hands and transferred to her grandson on his coming of age. The queen perished in prison. Nevertheless, Mangamma's place in history as a capable and enlightened ruler is unchallengeable.

Ahilya Bai Holkar (1725- 1795):

Ahilya Bai Holkar (r. 1767-1795), one of India's most revered rulers, was known as India's 'philosopher queen' for creating an island of peace and prosperity in her beautifully governed state of Indore during the turbulent 18th century. Malhar Rao Holkar was a chief general of Bajji Rao I. He rose rapidly until he became Peshwa's most trusted lieutenant. When Bajji Rao first distributed territories among his chief generals, Holkar, as the senior-most, received the best of the territories. Nearly two-fifths of Malwa was granted as 'saranjam' or territory for the maintenance of his army.

In 1733, when Malhar Rao was on his way back to the capital Indore, he saw the eight-year -old daughter of the village chief, Manikji Shinde and was impressed by his intelligence and regal bearing. He decided to marry her off to his only son, Khande Rao, who was ten years old at the time. Malhar Rao gave Ahilya Bai the best education of a prince offered at that time, along with religious and secular texts, the practice of arms, accounting, statecraft, and administration. Male Rao Ahilya Bai's son was born in 1745. Khande Rao was a pleasure-loving prince, and Malhar Rao had great faith in Ahilya Bai and her administration. She was extremely competent, and Malhar Rao continued to train her in administration and kept her informed about political movements. Khande Rao was unfortunately killed at a siege in Kumner. While all his

wives committed sati, Ahilya Bai was held back by his father-in-law as he implored her to live for the sake of an older man and her small children.

In 1761, Malhar left with his troops and fought valiantly in the first battle of Panipat, where he lost his life. Thereafter, Male Rao assumed full powers as Subedar. The British general Sir John Malcolm, who was involved in the Maratha wars and was the governor of Bombay, wrote about Ahilya Bai's life in his book *A Memoir of Central India*. Male Rao died within a year of coming to power, and his wife committed Sati; he had no children.

Thereafter, the issue of inheritance rose, and Ahilya Bai saw no reason why she could not herself become the official ruler. After a conflicting situation, Ahilya Bai, who was an embodiment of good virtues, became the ruler of Indore for the next 30 years. Her reign was considered extraordinary and one of the best in the country because of her system of governance. John Malcom writes 40 years after her death: "Her first principle of government appears to have been moderate assessment and respect for the native rights of the village officers.... She was always accessible, patient and unwearied". She wanted her subjects to prosper and was a great believer in individual rights to property. Indore grew into a mercantile centre because the laws were well implemented in its region.

Kittur Chennamma: (1778-1829)

Chennamma was the queen of Kittur, a small principality in North Karnataka. She refused to let the British annex her state in 1824 and fought them with great courage. She was the first woman freedom fighter before Rani of Jhansi and is a folk heroine in Karnataka. Airports, stadiums and ships are named after her, and her statues dot the landscape, notably the one in the Indian Parliament in Delhi. Chennamma was born in the village of Kakati in Kittur in 1778. She was the daughter of Dhulappagowda Desai and Padmavati Kakati, a jagir of 29 villages given by the Adil Sahis of Bijapur to her ancestors. She was proficient in Persian, Kannada, Marathi and Urdu. She gained knowledge in arts and music, received training in martial arts, swimming and spear throwing and was good at hunting too. She looked fair and beautiful, and her husband would often call her 'Chennagowri'. The folksongs of Karnataka tell of Chennamma's romantic meeting with Mallasarja Desai, the ruler of Kittur. They were married in Kakati in 1793 when she was 15 yrs old. Kittur was a small town of 280 villages near Dharwad in North Karnataka. Kittur's rulers remained as Bijapur's feudatories for many years. Three years later, in 1785, Kittur was captured by Haider's son Tippu Sultan of Mysore, who imprisoned Mallasarja in a fort. It was known that after three years, she was

sheltered by some relatives of his first wife, Rudramma. Kittur was handed over to the Marathas by Tipu.

Rudramma lived in amity with Chennamma. The former had two sons, Shivalingarudrasarja and Veerarudrasarja. Chennamma had a son, Shiva Basavaraj, and she concerned herself with the education of all. Chennamma was involved with the administration of the state, accompanying Mallasarja on expeditions and sitting with him in court. In 1816, after Mallasarja's death, his son Shivalingarudrasarja became the ruler. Chennamma was involved in the governance of Kittur for the next few years along with her stepson. After his death, the state fell under British rule. Chennamma and her nobles were horrified by Thackeray's (the collector/British official's) stance. Chennamma wrote repeatedly to the British officers; she spoke eloquently, preferring to fight to the death rather than relinquish her kingdom.

Countless statues immortalise her image facing the battlefield. Innumerable British soldiers were attacked, and Thackeray was shot down, and Elliot and Stevenson were captured and imprisoned. Chennamma and her people requested immediate adoption, else they threatened they would do something like jauhar; first kill both of them, then kill their women, including Rani Chennamma, rather than surrender. The British had no intention of giving in to Chennamma's demands. The populace cleaved to Chennamma, who reiterated that she only wanted her kingdom restored. The Kittur troops who engaged the British were defeated as the traitors had adulterated the gunpowder with millet and cow dung. Chennamma died in 1829, having dedicated her life to religious pursuits. Chennamma's relentless spirit of independence is celebrated by girls across the country, who are draped in Lingayat-style saris and recite lines immortalised in a movie named after her.

Lakshmibai, R. of Jhansi: (1835-1858)

Manikarnika was the rani's original name and was born in 1828 at Assi Ghat in Varanasi to Moropant Tambe, a Brahmin by birth who was part of the small court of the exiled Peshwa Baji Rao II. Her father took care of her as her mother had died. Manu would spend her time with her father like any other Marathi boy or girl: as she learnt to wrestle and ride, shoot, and wield the sword. She was interested in scriptures, administration strategy and war. She knew Marathi, Hindi, Sanskrit and Persian and spent time reading epics and heroic tales of Shivaji. Her exceptional nature was noticed by a priest searching for a suitable Brahmin bride for the widowed and childless king of Jhansi, Gangadhar Rao. As the chance to be a queen was a rare one, the proposal was accepted. She married in Jhansi and was given the new name

Lakshmi Bai. Initially, she lived as a traditional royal woman. She had a son, Damodar Rao. After Gangadhar Rao's death from illness, the rani wrote to Dalhousie, the then-governor general, requesting that Damodhar Rao be recognised as the ruler of Jhansi. However, Dalhousie, the British governor general, claimed Jhansi, and in February 1854, he signed an order to acquire it. This enraged Rani, and she was not prepared to give up. Instead, she hired a British lawyer, John Lang. He met her in Jhansi. This is how he described her: "A woman of about middle size... (Her face) Even now it had many charms The expression ... very intelligent.... A remarkably fine figure she had. (Gupta 254)

Soon, the mutiny began in Meerut on 10 May 1857, when Indian troops attacked British officers and took control, making Bahadur Shah Zafar their leader. One can only remember Rani as an inspirational ruler of Jhansi, always fighting to regain Jhansi. Her vision was that of a fair and just society, and people were ready to die for her. She created a women's troop, which comprised three thousand women, as she would train these women in her palace grounds: eventually, they died fighting the British and were buried together in Jhansi. The rani dressed in a Pathan-style outfit would ride all over the fort, inspiring her people, would exercise like a warrior, wrestling, weightlifting, wearing a waistcoat and a fanned turban.

During her brief nine-month reign, she fought many battles. Her bravery knew no bounds. She even went after the decoits, defeated the decoit chief Sagar Singh, who later joined her troop. She even introduced currency in her own name and hoisted the red Jhansi flag. She encountered the British at Bhandar and escaped after hand-to-hand combat; the next day, when she rode 160 km, her new horse refused to jump a small stream. She was injured and later reached a small temple near Phoolbagh, where she passed away. The rani and her valiant struggle are still remembered today, as she is the national heroine celebrated not only for her valour but also for envisioning an all-inclusive society that is just and fair.

Discussion

The historical account of the five powerful warriors offers a glimpse of their fascinating lives, leaving an indelible impression on Indian history. These five women are worth knowing and writing about, not just because they ruled, but because they ruled well, at levels comparable to those of male rulers or even beyond. So, these are amazing narratives of exceptional women with myriad facets of their personalities that can be recounted in Indian history. They have been rulers who have paved the way, bringing in and shaping a progressive world. No pathway was created for them. Even

after occupying the throne, they have faced stiff internal resistance from their nobles, who have shown disregard or disapproval toward their own people, as well as from external rulers who considered them weak and easy to conquer. Nevertheless, they did rule with grit and determination.

Conclusion

The history of our freedom movement is replete with the saga of bravery, sacrifice and political sagacity of countless women of our country. Rani Durgavati was known for her exceptional qualities, courage, and counsel, bringing the whole of that country under her control. Rani Mangammal of Madurai, a great administrator, built alliances when fighting for a kingdom was the order of the day. In the 18th century, Ahilya Bai's Indore was by far the best-governed state in India. Moreover, at a time when the British East India Company sought to occupy India, Tipu Sultan had been eliminated, the proud Marathas humbled, and Rani Chennamma devised machinations as the British tried to annex her kingdom, Kittur. Another woman warrior who has made a powerful impact on the minds of Indian people is the Rani of Jhansi, Lakshmi Bai. Protesting against the 'Doctrine of Lapse,' she refused to surrender Jhansi and fought bravely during the Revolt of 1857 and died on the battlefield fighting the British forces. Her courage remains an inspiration for many Indian women to rise against the forces. These women governed, built roads, exhibited their talents and patronised the arts and sciences. These narrative accounts of valour and diplomacy, leadership and wit continue to inspire us even today. They portray different facets of their personalities. These are, invariably, portraits of courageous and intelligent women who were leaders in their own right. These heroic rulers have daringly forged new paths while seeking a sense of identity.

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Works Cited

Gupta, Archana Garodia. *The Women Who Ruled India: Leaders, Warriors, Icons*. Hachette Book Publishing India LTD, Gurugram, 2019.

Madhavananda, Swami, Majumdar and Ramesh Chandra. (Ed) *Great Women of India*.
Advaita Ashrama, Delhi.

Malcolm, John. *A Memoir of Central India: Including Malwa and Adjoining Provinces*.
Muntakhab-Ut-Tawarikh. .Lowe, H., Tr Vol 2., p. 65

Rao, Velcheru Narayana; Shulman, David Dean; Subrahmanyam, Sanjay. *Symbols of
Substance: Court and State in Nayaka Period Tamilnadu*.

Sundaram, Bhavani. *Unseen and Unheard Women Warriors of Independent India*.
Notion Press, 2022.

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